

A decorative graphic on the left side of the slide, consisting of a vertical line of small circles connected by thin lines, resembling a circuit board or a data stream. The lines and circles are white and set against a dark blue background.

EXPLORING COLLABORATIVE CYBER ATTACK RESPONSE OF AUTOMOTIVE SYSTEMS

INTRODUCTION

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

- Vehicles are operated by millions of individuals every day
- Vehicles are getting more complex
 - Made from network of nodes
 - Wide connectivity to their surroundings
- 5G provides high bandwidth with milliseconds of latencies
 - More services
 - Wider connectivity

INTRODUCTION

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

- Vehicles are safety and real-time critical systems
 - Openness to the Internet raises cyber security concerns
- More connectivity would provide more services
 - More entry points for cyber attacks
- Cyber attacks target different assets
 - Software, hardware, data storage, and network/communications
- Different attributes can be attacked
 - Vehicle performance, privacy, or even safety

INTRODUCTION

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

- Many security standards and protocols are being researched continuously
 - But eventually, attacks would happen
 - Attack on Sony's PlayStation Network
 - EX-CEO of Sony, Howard Stringer : "Nobody's system is 100% secure"
- An extra effort could be spent on cyber attack response techniques
 - To reduce the impact of cyber attacks
 - Minimize losses

INTRODUCTION

PURPOSE OF STUDY

- Explore available cyber attack response techniques on the software asset
- Design and develop a **collaborative** framework to evaluate cyber attack response techniques

RESPONSE TECHNIQUES FOR THE SOFTWARE ASSET [1]

[1] T. Rosenstatter, K. Strandberg, R. Jolak, R. Scandariato, and T. Olovsson. REMIND: A Framework for the Resilient Design of Automotive Systems. In 2020 IEEE Secure Development (SecDev), pages 81–95. IEEE, 9 2020

MAIN IDEA

- The aim is to develop a framework that allows multiple connected vehicles to collaborate on finding out the best cyber attack response technique for a specific cyber attack that happens in real time
- This is done by the following:
 - Each vehicle would use a different response technique
 - A simulation of the attack will be performed on the vehicles
 - Each vehicle would then use that response technique assigned to it and logs data (e.g. CPU usage, time, etc)
 - Based on the logs, the best response technique would then be picked and pushed

ASSUMPTIONS

- Response techniques are already implemented in the server and vehicles
- Collaboration is done on vehicles with the same software version and same hardware specifications
- There is some defense mechanism (e.g. IDS) that identifies/detects the threat/anomaly
- There is some mechanism that triggers the use of a response technique, i.e. after detecting the threat

DESIGN OF THE FRAMEWORK

- Architecture
 - Peer-to-Peer (P2P)
 - Vehicles communicate with each other
 - No central entity required
 - Vehicles collaborate on finding the best response technique
 - Client-Server
 - Vehicles connect to a server
 - The server manages the operations

DESIGN OF THE FRAMEWORK

- Experimentation
 - Continuous Experimentation process
 - Run multiple versions of a software
 - Evaluate them
 - Adopt the best variant

Initialization

